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Adaptation of teaching and assessment to students' ambition levels

Kjell Staffas

Uppsala University
Uppsala, Sweden

Steffi Knorn

Uppsala University
Uppsala, Sweden

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ABSTRACT

Three different groups of engineering students took the course Signals & systems in a teaching approach, which they perceived as radically new and different. In the course, their only physical contact with the teacher was one weekly hour at their disposal. Apart from this, students were encouraged to use provided material for self study. When taught in a more traditional way, students used to have trouble fulfilling all learning goals for the course. The study's aim was to investigate students' capability to adapt to this model and their experiences from a motivational and performative view. A mixed methods approach was used with interviews, a written questionnaire and a comparison of the grades from previous years. The students' performed considerably better on the exam, but experienced difficulties in adapting to the newer format, and many fell back in a more common passive role, despite taking part in the new activities. Only a small group changed their study routine according to the intention from the teachers. The main criticism concerned the absence of traditional lecturing. The study clearly shows that students can change and perform better but are also stuck in a teaching tradition that they are used to. They perform better in groups, and can adapt from fellow students that change their study routine. This paper gives valuable insights in what students fostered in "traditional teaching" experience from a format where they are responsible for these parts of the teaching, and how they use their time with the teacher. Future investigations should include motivation from lectures, improvement of metacognitive skills and degrees of self-regulation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The planning and development of most university courses is still heavily based on a traditional format including informative lectures, presenting problems solutions on the board and fill in the blanks laboratory work. Of course, there exist initiatives on engaging the students in communicating during lectures and lessons, and other inputs to make the laboratory work more investigative. Nevertheless, apart from potential issues in implementing alternative teaching methods, teachers also face resistance from students as many of them express that they are perfectly happy with a course in the traditional format. Thus, courses often contain no surprises and the lectures include what students can expect from the exam [1].

Efforts on transforming education to a more student-centered approach is far more than applying a model that proved to be engaging and motivating. From experience on tutoring teachers in higher education, efforts tend to bring the teachers to a frustrating moment in their course where they realize that people are lazy by nature. Fostered in a traditional format of teaching student become insecure on what to expect from a newer model and what is expected from them. It is far from obvious that they become more active just because the teachers have learned some new tricks up their sleeve.

Therefore, a change towards more student-centered learning activities requires a transformation in the teacher's own approach as an expert and facilitator to deep knowledge. This transformation is perhaps the most difficult part of the new format: How to take part in the learning process? Generally, there are fewer relations between study success and methods and habits, than between study results and attitudes and motivation [2]. Therefore, the key role for the teacher, besides being the expert, is to create an engaging and motivating environment for the students. I.e. the presence of the teacher is not very important but instead the process among the students and the motivation and drive of the students is what counts and should be strived for.

2 RESEARCH QUESTION

In this study, we aim to test and evaluate how different teaching activities are suitable or can be adapted to students' abilities and ambition levels. The course goals and required levels for passing the course and achieving higher grades were communicated to the students in a clear and efficient fashion. Given those goals and requirements, we investigate the students' ability to take responsibility for their learning as well as efficiently plan their time and study activities.

3 METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH

This inquiry is based on

- quantitative comparison of exam results;
- a questionnaire investigating students' experience of learning, adaptation and alignment to the different teaching approach and learning activities from their ambition and abilities; and
- fourteen interviews with selected students,

a mixed methods approach is preferred [3]. The collected data mainly covers students' own actions and reactions to the new format, which gives the survey a narrative view from experience [4].

4 STUDENT-CENTERED LEARNING (SCL)

The main difference between a "passive learning environment" and a more active is, instead of transferring knowledge to students, to engage them in a collaborate process of continuously building and reshaping their understanding naturally connected to their experiences and interactions with the world [5]. All learning is of course active so the meaning is more of the difference between activities that promote surface learning compared to deep learning. To prevent students from surface learning one must remove the factors that guide them not to learn in depth [6]. For good teaching to

promote effective learning, [7] summarize four shared focus-areas from a constructivist approach:

- 1) Focus on who is doing the learning
- 2) Focus on the context
- 3) Focus on the kind of learning task being undertaken
- 4) Focus on the processes involved

To become a constructivist teacher in higher education, [8] suggests the following guiding principles:

- 1) Posing problems of emerging relevance to students
- 2) Structuring learning around primary concepts
- 3) Seeking and valuing students' points of view
- 4) Adapting curriculum to address students' suppositions
- 5) Assessing student learning in the context of teaching

There are several frameworks for SCL. Keller's ARCS model aims at enhance attention, relevance, confidence and satisfaction (hence the abbreviation ARCS) through a motivational design approach [9]. [10] suggests that learner-centered approaches focus on the unique individuality of varying interests, capacities, backgrounds and perspectives, and how to support it. In order to increase ownership for the students, [5] proposed the REAL (Rich environments for active learning) model. Focusing on the social aspect of SCL, [11] capitalized on active learning and facilitation via social media. There are also proposed models that assume students to perform independently without external guidance [12]. This is similar to different problem- and project based learning approaches (PBL).

The approach underlying the model used in the framework for this paper is more like the proposed model from [13]: To encompass motivational, cognitive, social and affective aspects of learning, the following constructs of SCL are keys:

- a) Autonomy from self-determination theory
- b) Scaffolding from constructivism
- c) Authentic audience from constructionism

This is the Own it, Learn it, and Share it (OLSit) framework.

5 THE COGNITIVE AND MOTIVATIONAL DIMENSIONS OF (SELFDIRECTED) LEARNING

Already Dewey presented in his early work that the ultimate challenge in designing an educational experience is the integration and coordination of cognitive and social concerns [14]. From the constructivist approach, the focus is on the learning process itself, not the teacher or teaching. A model of self-directed learning is proposed by [15]:

- External management (contextual control)
- Internal monitoring (cognitive responsibility)
- Motivational (entering and task) issues associated with learning in an educational context

The learners shall "...assume personal responsibility and collaborative control of the cognitive (self-monitoring) and contextual (self-management) processes in constructing and confirming meaningful and worthwhile learning outcomes." (ibid. p. 18). To create a motivating and inspiring learning environment the following content was presented:

- A course compendium written for the course, including dedicated exercises;
- Worked out solutions for all exercises of the course compendium;
- Conceptual questions with solutions for each course week's material;
- Video recordings of lectures covering most of the material in the course compendium;
- A summary for each course week including a list of recommended reading material, video lectures and exercises to be solved;
- An explanation of each course goal, including a break down into which subparts are required for passing the course or receiving higher grades and related, relevant material such as parts in the compendium, video lectures and exercises.

This was a 5 credits course given at 1/3 speed which means eight weeks in total. Students were divided into small groups of up to 8 students of their choice, i.e., students were asked to join a group freely. Then, each student group got one hour of scheduled time (referred to as "lesson" or "meeting") with the head teacher of the course per teaching week, which could be used according to the students' choice. Options included explanations of some material, solving examples, answering questions, giving feedback on students' work or free discussions. The remaining time was intended to be used for self-organized study activities for the course but no specific times were formally scheduled for the students for such activities. Students were encouraged to follow the week plans, organize their time as well as study the material according to their ambition (wishing to achieve a higher mark or just passing) and ability (allowing for less time to be spent in case of good prior knowledge and providing extra material for students with insufficient prior knowledge) and prepare for the weekly meetings with the teacher. However, teachers did not check whether students followed these recommendations. The course planning was also adapted by a fellow teacher on the same course in another program (the control group) without further influence from the other two courses/teachers. None of the teachers was specially trained for this teaching approach. Rather, they have experience using both traditional and other SCL approaches. Both teachers also taught the courses before and are well familiar with the contents.

6 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we followed a mixed method approach using answers to a written questionnaire, semi-structured interviews and a comparison of the grades from previous years. We included students from two engineering programs taking very similar courses, which were taught with the novel teaching approach by the same teacher and of which we interviewed nine students (five from one program and four from the other). For comparison, we also considered students of a third engineering

program (control group) taking the same course, with the same teaching approach but another, experienced teacher. We interviewed five students of the control group.

6.1 Results from interviews and course survey

It became apparent that it is far from easy to implement methods that should nurture SCL: it can backfire and make the students passive, i.e. they use the non-scheduled time studying other parallel courses instead. In addition, it is hard to let go of the lecturing part of sessions and meeting students in smaller groups need to be focusing on what the group actually asks for. This is both a challenge for students, who reported that they needed time to adapt to the new approach and reflect about their needs and preferences, as well as teachers, who were tempted to fall back into the traditional lecturing role. Specially, when groups were merged (in the control group) to give each group more time, i.e., then 2 hours per larger group instead of one hour per small group, the lessons more often became mini lectures. Therefore, the teacher's role is utterly important and he/she needs to leave the lecture suit in the office. It is about being perceptive to what the students are there for. Then it becomes even more important to give them instructions on what to work on to prepare for the meetings with the teacher. As [13] puts it: "...SCL is a complex learning process that students must be thoroughly supported in the motivational, cognitive and social aspects.". Hence, instead of converting the sessions into lectures, teachers must instead challenge the students into taking responsibility for their learning, explore the material and prepare questions or at least form an opinion about how the lesson should best be used.

In fact, comparing answers from the two programs and the control group revealed that a mayor distinguishing factor between students, that benefited and appreciated the teaching approach, and others, who did not, was the insight that the courses' teaching approach required students to take responsibility for their learning. Out of the five students interviewed from the control group, who all disliked the teaching approach, only one mentioned the need to take responsibility for organizing and planning the learning activities. The remaining students instead expressed a strong wish to be taught in the traditional lecture format, which they are used to. A loss of interest in the course and difficulties in learning the material was hence mainly blamed on the absence of lectures. The only positive aspect of not having lectures for them was the freedom to use the time for other activities such as studying for other courses. However, they also admitted that using the time for studying for the other courses worsened the situation as it became even harder to follow the course in the new teaching format, which led some of them to give up on the course all together (at least for some time).

In contrast, the majority of students from the first two programs, brought up the need to take responsibility for their learning, including to organize their time and motivate themselves to study the material as well as prepare for the lessons, in the interviews. While they agreed with the control group, that this aspect was challenging (especially at first), they acknowledged its necessity in order to prompt students to become active learners. Further, some reflected that they felt more "in phase" with the course in the new teaching program compared to the parallel courses in the traditional format, as they became more active in learning and preparing for the lessons.

Students in the two programs reported a high level of deep learning and expect to remember the course material longer. In contrast, when asking the same question to students in the control group, they indicated that their learning was more superficial and focused on learning in order to pass the exam, which they started to prepare for admittedly late. Indeed, some detailed that they did not grasp how different parts of the material connected and were missing the overall picture in the course. This partly contradicts the common believe (especially among students) that lectures allow to give a comprehensive overview of the material and facilitate general understanding of the material since the control group also reported to have perceived the lessons as predominantly lectures.

Several students from the two courses admitted that they did not like the teaching approach at the beginning of the course mostly because it was perceived as unusual, uncomfortable and partly scary. However, after getting over initial deprecative responses, students reported that they changed their attitude and appreciate the benefits of being forced to grapple with the material. Hence, even in a relatively short period of time (6-7 weeks of teaching) students can adapt and change their attitude towards teaching approaches, their study routine and sense of responsibility. However, whether they do, seems to depend to a large degree on the teacher, since students in the control group did not report such change of mind.

Another aspect to facilitate students to take responsibility for their learning and change their study routine towards an active role might be the group size. Despite some students complaining about shortage of time, groups were kept as small as intended (with up to eight students) in the two courses, which allowed for only one hour per group per week. An additional lunch meeting, open for all students, and prompt responses to requests sent via email offered some relief of the time problem. This seemed to have been a worthwhile decision as students expressed feelings of confidence and safety when being able to ask questions in front of only a few fellow students.

In contrast, in the control group, the teacher decided to join two groups at a time in order to allow for more time per group with now up to 16 students. This led to a greater tendency of converting the lessons into lectures, as discussed above. Also, 16 appears to be too large of a group to feel confident about asking questions openly. Students in the control group instead indicated that they perceived no difference in asking a question in the groups of 16 students compared to their entire class of around 90 students. Hence, there seems to be a critical group size below 16 to ensure students feel confident and secure to be honest and open to ask questions and seek help. Another factor might be that students in the control group chose who to form a (small) group with but were then combined with another group solely by convenience of the teaching schedule but not allowing students to choose how groups should be joined. Both aspects are important to guide students and build up their confidence such that they are able to then take an active role in their learning.

6.2 Exam results

The exam was graded on the scale “Fail/3/4/5 (highest mark)” and included one part per each of the 5 course goals. For each course goal, students needed to pass one

basic part in order to pass the exam, i.e. receive mark 3. The basic parts were only marked as pass or fail. Further, in order to receive a higher mark, students could choose to answer additional questions (clearly marked as “for higher grades”). Marks 4 and 5 were then awarded depending on points earned for the more advanced parts. Which kind of knowledge was expected for each course goal, both for passing / basic as well as for higher grades, was clearly communicated to the students at the beginning of the course. Hence, students could adapt their study activities during the course and which questions to answer during the exam depending on their ambition level.

The following table shows an overview of the exam results for all three courses (abbreviated by “C” and C3 being the third course given to the control group) for the autumn semester 2017 and the autumn semester 2018. Note that the exam structure was the same in both academic years but in autumn 2017, all three courses were given with flipped lectures (for the entire class) and tutorials (in large groups of up to 50 students).

Table 1. Exam results

	C1 (2017)	C2 (2017)	C3 (2017)	C1 (2018)	C2 (2018)	C3 (2018)
Pass (tot, %)	21, 36.8%	23, 41.1%	56, 61.5%	22, 45.8%	38, 77.6%	62, 78.5%
Fail (tot, %)	36, 63.2%	36, 58.9%	35, 38.5%	26, 54.2%	11, 22.4%	17, 21.5%
Ave. mark	3.29	3.35	3.7	3.41	3.53	3.22

It is interesting to see that in all three courses (including the control group C3), the pass rate increased. In fact, in course 2 it increased so significantly that further investigation is needed to understand potential other factors, that might have contributed to the result. However, only in C1 and C2 the average mark (only calculated from the pass grades, so excluding the “fail”) increased, which means that not only students grasped the basic concepts better (leading to a higher pass rate) but also did better in the harder parts of the exam, which required higher taxonomy levels (leading to an increase in average grade). This is particularly interesting, as it indicates that the teaching method benefited strong students (getting better marks) and weaker students (helping them to pass). In case the teaching method would have only helped weak students to pass, the average mark should have dropped. Likewise, in case the teaching method would only benefit higher achieving students, the pass rate might even have fallen or remained the same with a higher average mark.

Note that the control group (C3) clearly also benefited in terms of achieving a higher pass rate. However, in contrast to C1 and C2, the average grade dropped from 3.7 to 3.22, i.e. much more than the increase in C1 and C2. This hints on that the method mainly benefited weak students (that only achieved grade 3) or that students achieved less deep knowledge and hence got less points in the more difficult parts for higher grades, which required higher taxonomy levels. Another aspect might be that students in the control group might have been less interested in learning for the course and hence chose to only try to pass the exam. This is particularly interesting as the students in the control group (taking C3) are considered as very ambitious and very

knowledgeable (see for example their average pass rate and mark in 2017 in contrast to C1 and C2).

7 SUMMARY

It should be noted that despite the majority of the students in the two programs appreciated the course structure towards the end of the course and acknowledged that they learned a lot, their initial rejection or at least distrust had to be dealt with and overcome. Students complained about the teaching method in different forms and expressed strong discomfort, especially at the beginning of the course. Also, despite the pass rates and average grade improving in both programs, the student rating in the final survey did not improve much. Hence, one conclusion might be that effective SCL and teaching does not guarantee that students appreciate it or feel comfortable.

8 FUTURE QUESTIONS TO INVESTIGATE

- Can students' content be improved by adding some lectures (as requested) without compromising the positive effects of the group teaching mode (such as increased passing grade)?
- Are students in some programs more or less prone to benefit from the small group teaching?
- Will students retain their knowledge achieved through the small group teaching longer?
- Do students improve their metacognitive skills by being forced to be more self-steered and self-organized when using small group teaching?
- Would students respond more positively when being taught with this method in first year, i.e., before being overly used to classical lectures?
- Would students' opinions on this teaching method change when being more used to it, e.g. by being taught in this form also in a subsequent course?

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